

BIOREMEDIATION POTENTIAL OF BACTERIAL STRAINS ISOLATED FROM OIL-CONTAMINATED SOILS UNDER THE CONDITIONS OF THE SURKHANDARYA REGION

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot “Petromaruz-O‘zbekiston” MChJ hududidagi neft va neft mahsulotlari bilan ifloslangan tuproqlarda mikroorganizmlarning biologik xususiyatlarini o‘rganishga qaratilgan. Mikrobiologik tahlillar natijasida turli hududlardan olingan tuproq va neft mahsulotlari namunalarida Gram-musbat va Gram-manfiy, aerob va anaerob mikroorganizmlar mavjudligi aniqlangan. Ajratilgan shtammlar orasida aborigen bakteriyalar uglevodorodlarni parchalash va neftni bioremediatsiya qilish qobiliyatiga ega bo‘lib, 2% neft muhitida ham yuqori faollik namoyon qilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari mahalliy mikrofloradan samarali neft-destruktsiya qiluvchi shtammlarni ajratib olish va ularni ekologik toza biotexnologik usullarda qo‘llash imkoniyatini tasdiqlaydi. Ushbu yondashuv neft bilan ifloslangan tuproqlarni tozalash va ekotizimni tiklashda samarali va xavfsiz usul sifatida ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so‘zlar: Neft bilan ifloslangan tuproq, mikroorganizmlar, bioremediatsiya, uglevodorodlar degradatsiyasi, aborigen shtammlar, ekologik tozalash, biotexnologik usullar, tuproq mikroflorasi, neft mahsulotlari, biologik faollik

Аннотация. Данное исследование было направлено на изучение биологических свойств микроорганизмов в почвах, загрязнённых нефтью и нефтепродуктами, на территории ООО «Petromaruz-Uzbekistan». В результате микробиологических анализов в образцах почвы и нефтепродуктов, взятых из различных участков, были выявлены грамположительные и грамотрицательные, аэробные и анаэробные микроорганизмы. Среди выделенных штаммов аборигенные бактерии продемонстрировали способность разлагать углеводороды и осуществлять биоремедиацию нефти, проявляя высокую активность даже в среде с 2% нефти. Результаты исследования подтверждают возможность выделения эффективных нефтеразрушающих штаммов из местной микрофлоры и их применения в экологически безопасных биотехнологических методах. Этот подход имеет важное значение как эффективный и безопасный способ очистки почв, загрязнённых нефтью, и восстановления экосистемы.

Ключевые слова: Почва, загрязнённая нефтью, микроорганизмы, биоремедиация, деградация углеводородов, аборигенные штаммы, экологическая очистка, биотехнологические методы, микрофлора почвы, нефтепродукты, биологическая активность

Annotation. This study was aimed at investigating the biological properties of microorganisms in soils contaminated with oil and petroleum products at the territory of “Petromaruz-Uzbekistan” LLC. Microbiological analyses revealed the presence of Gram-positive and Gram-negative, aerobic and anaerobic microorganisms in soil and petroleum product samples collected from different sites. Among the isolated strains, indigenous bacteria demonstrated the ability to degrade hydrocarbons and perform oil bioremediation, showing high

activity even in a medium containing 2% oil. The research results confirm the possibility of isolating effective oil-degrading strains from local microflora and applying them in environmentally safe biotechnological methods. This approach is considered an efficient and safe method for cleaning oil-contaminated soils and restoring ecosystems.

Keywords: Oil-contaminated soil, microorganisms, bioremediation, hydrocarbon degradation, indigenous strains, environmental remediation, biotechnological methods, soil microflora, petroleum products, biological activity.

One of the most urgent ecological issues is the degradation of the environment brought on by the extraction, processing, and transportation of oil and petroleum products. The biological diversity of natural landscapes is greatly diminished, vegetation cover deteriorates, and soil fertility declines as a result of such pollution [1]. The activity of living things is negatively impacted when oil seeps into the soil, changing its morphological, physical, and chemical characteristics. As a result, it is now crucial to address the problem of cleaning up petroleum-contaminated landscapes using environmentally friendly techniques. Utilizing hydrocarbon-oxidizing microbes has been seen as a successful strategy in recent years for lowering pollution from oil and petroleum products [2]. These microbes can break down the complex molecules found in oil into simpler, safer products like carbon dioxide and water thanks to their enzymatic systems. However, it is unreasonable to anticipate all chemicals to be destroyed concurrently by a single bacterium because oil is made up of hundreds of different chemical components. Consequently, it is thought to be appropriate to employ consortia of different hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria in the creation of efficient biopreparations [3,4]. The process of bioremediation of hydrocarbon-contaminated soils is acknowledged as being low-cost, efficient, and safe for the environment. The establishment of ideal conditions to promote microbial activity, the chemical makeup of hydrocarbons in the contaminated environment, the hydrocarbons' molecular structure, and their bioavailability to microorganisms are some of the variables that affect how well the biodegradation process works [5].

In order to learn more about the biological characteristics of microorganisms, experimental investigations were carried out on soils contaminated with petroleum products on 1.8 hectares of land owned by “ Petromaruz-Uzbekistan ” LLC. With summer temperatures as high as +44.8 °C and winter temperatures as low as -20.5 °C, the study site has a distinctly continental climate. The early precipitation is 144.6 mm, and the average temperature is +16.2 °C. With raw materials from the Surkhandarya region's Jarkurgan, Kumkurgan, Shurchi, and Termez oil fields, the company can process 250,000 tons of oil annually. Bitumen, fuel oil, diesel fuel, and gasoline (AI-80) are the products of the production. 400 g samples were taken from different soil depths (0–5 cm, 5–10 cm, and 15–30 cm) for microbiological examination in order to examine the dynamics and dispersion of microbial communities. Furthermore, samples were collected from petroleum wastes and products, including paraffin, reservoir sludge, oil sludge waste, oil + water, oil-separated water, and oil.

Results. Microbiological studies revealed the presence of diverse microorganisms in soil and petroleum product samples collected from different locations. In the soil sample taken from the temporary waste storage site, a Gram-positive, aerobic, spherical-shaped culture of *Dietzia maris* was identified. In the samples of oil-separated water, a Gram-positive, aerobic, oval-shaped *Rothia endophytica*; a Gram-negative, aerobic, rod-shaped *Acinetobacter lwoffii*; as well as Gram-positive, spherical *Rhizobium radiobacter* strains were isolated. In the soil sample collected near the oil loading terminal of the Lalmikor field, Gram-negative, aerobic, rod-shaped

Pseudomonas fluorescens and spore-forming, motile, rod-shaped *Alkalihalobacillus clausii* (previously known as *Bacillus clausii*) were identified. In the oil sludge (reservoir) sample and in the soil sample collected near the bitumen loading terminal, a Gram-positive, anaerobic, rod-shaped culture of *Bacillus subtilis* was identified. From the soil sample taken near the bitumen loading terminal, strains of *Bacillus simplex* and *Bacillus licheniformis* were isolated. From the soil sample collected near the treatment facility, a culture of *Actinomyces oris* was isolated. In the oil sludge (reservoir) sample, a strain of *Streptomyces rochei* was identified. The conducted studies evaluated the viability, growth activity, and hydrocarbon-degrading capacity of microorganisms under oil-contaminated conditions [6] For this purpose, a solid nutrient medium was prepared by supplementing Raymond medium ($\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 - 0.1$; $\text{CaCl}_2 - 0.1$; $\text{MnSO}_4 - 0.02$; $\text{FeSO}_4 - 0.01$; $\text{MgSO}_4 - 0.2$; $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl} - 0.2$; $\text{NaCl} - 3$; $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 - 1.5$; $\text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4 - 1$) with 1% oil and 2% agar. The medium was sterilized in an autoclave at 120 °C under 1 atm pressure for 30 minutes, after which it was poured into Petri dishes and left to solidify. Four bacterial strains were inoculated into each Petri dish and incubated in a thermostat at 37 °C. During incubation, colony formation activity and growth rates were monitored. After qualitative analysis, 14 strains out of a total of 24 isolates were selected based on high growth performance. At the next stage, these strains were retested in Raymond medium supplemented with 2% oil. The results showed that indigenous bacteria were present in the soils around the “Jarkurgan-oil” field, with 14 out of 24 isolates demonstrating the ability to grow under oil-contaminated conditions, and 9 of these strains exhibiting high activity even in the presence of 2% oil [7].

Conclusion. The conducted studies demonstrated that indigenous microorganisms are present in the soils surrounding the “Jarkurgan-oil” field, which are highly adapted to oil-contaminated environments and possess hydrocarbon-degrading capabilities. Among the isolated strains, 14 out of 24 showed the ability to grow under oil-contaminated conditions, and 9 of these exhibited high activity even in the presence of 2% oil. This indicates the potential to isolate effective oil-degrading strains from the composition of the local microflora. The identified strains actively participate in the processes of hydrocarbon assimilation and degradation, making them promising for enhancing the efficiency of bioremediation in soils contaminated with petroleum products. Thus, the development of environmentally friendly biotechnological methods based on these strains is of great importance not only for environmental cleanup but also for preserving natural resources and agricultural productivity. Oil pollution severely restricts growth and development processes in biocenoses, reduces biological diversity, and disrupts the natural balance of ecosystems. Therefore, the use of biological methods is considered one of the most appropriate approaches for cleaning soils contaminated with petroleum products. The bioremediation process carried out by microorganisms not only degrades hydrocarbons but also detoxifies harmful compounds, thereby contributing to the restoration of ecosystems. Overall, the obtained results justify the use of local bacterial strains for the bioremediation of oil-contaminated areas under the conditions of the Surkhandarya region. In the future, the development of biopreparations based on these strains and their application in practice will serve as effective measures in environmental protection.

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